

MORE RESULTS AND APPLICATIONS OF THE GENERALIZED SMARANDACHE STAR FUNCTION

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ABSTRACT: In [1] we define SMARANDACHE FACTOR PARTITION FUNCTION , as follows:

Let $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_r$ be a set of r natural numbers and $p_1, p_2, p_3, \dots, p_r$ be arbitrarily chosen distinct primes then $F(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_r)$ called the Smarandache Factor Partition of $(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_r)$ is defined as the number of ways in which the number

$N = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} p_3^{\alpha_3} \dots p_r^{\alpha_r}$ could be expressed as the product of its' divisors. For simplicity , we denote $F(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_r) = F'(N)$,where

$$N = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} p_3^{\alpha_3} \dots p_r^{\alpha_r} \dots p_n^{\alpha_n}$$

and p_r is the r^{th} prime. $p_1 = 2, p_2 = 3$ etc.

Also for the case

$$\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = \alpha_3 = \dots = \alpha_r = \dots = \alpha_n = 1$$

Let us denote

$$F(1, 1, 1, 1, 1, \dots) = F(1\#n)$$

← n - ones →

In [2] we define **The Generalized Smarandache Star**

Function as follows:

Smarandache Star Function

$$(1) \quad F''(N) = \sum_{d|N} F'(d_r) \quad \text{where } d_r | N$$

$$(2) \quad F'''(N) = \sum_{d_r|N} F''(d_r)$$

d_r ranges over all the divisors of N .

If N is a square free number with n prime factors, let us denote

$$F'''(N) = F''(1\#n)$$

Smarandache Generalised Star Function

$$(3) \quad F'^{n*}(N) = \sum_{d_r|N} F'^{(n-1)*}(d_r) \quad n > 1$$

and d_r ranges over all the divisors of N .

For simplicity we denote

$$F'(Np_1p_2 \dots p_n) = F'(N@1\#n), \text{ where}$$

$$(N, p_i) = 1 \text{ for } i = 1 \text{ to } n \text{ and each } p_i \text{ is a prime.}$$

$F'(N@1\#n)$ is nothing but the Smarandache factor partition of (a number N multiplied by n primes which are coprime to N).

In [3] I had derived a general result on the Smarandache Generalised Star Function. In the present note some more results and applications of Smarandache Generalised Star Function are explored and derived.

DISCUSSION:

THEOREM(4.1) :

$$F'^{n*}(p^\alpha) = \sum_{k=0}^{\alpha} {}^{n+k-1}C_{n-1} P(\alpha-k) \quad \text{-----(4.1)}$$

Following proposition shall be applied in the proof of this

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\alpha} {}^{r+k-1}C_{r-1} = {}^{\alpha+r}C_r \quad \text{-----(4.2)}$$

Let the proposition (4.1) be true for $n = r$ to $n = 1$.

$$F'^{r*}(p^\alpha) = \sum_{k=0}^{\alpha} {}^{r+k-1}C_{r-1} P(\alpha-k) \quad \text{-----(4.3)}$$

$$F'^{(r+1)*}(p^\alpha) = \sum_{t=0}^{\alpha} F'^{r*}(p^t)$$

(p ranges over all the divisors of p^α for $t = 0$ to α)

$$\text{RHS} = F'^{r*}(p^\alpha) + F'^{r*}(p^{\alpha-1}) + F'^{r*}(p^{\alpha-2}) + \dots + F'^{r*}(p) + F'^{r*}(1)$$

from the proposition (4.3) we have

$$F'^{r*}(p^\alpha) = \sum_{k=0}^{\alpha} {}^{r+k-1}C_{r-1} P(\alpha-k)$$

expanding RHS from $k = 0$ to α

$$F'^{r*}(p^\alpha) = {}^{r+\alpha-1}C_{r-1} P(0) + {}^{r+\alpha-2}C_{r-1} P(1) + \dots + {}^{r-1}C_{r-1} P(\alpha)$$

similarly

$$F'^{r*}(p^{\alpha-1}) = {}^{r+\alpha-2}C_{r-1} P(0) + {}^{r+\alpha-3}C_{r-1} P(1) + \dots + {}^{r-1}C_{r-1} P(\alpha-1)$$

$$F'^{r*}(p^{\alpha-2}) = {}^{r+\alpha-3}C_{r-1} P(0) + {}^{r+\alpha-4}C_{r-1} P(1) + \dots + {}^{r-1}C_{r-1} P(\alpha-2)$$

.

$$F^{r*}(p) = {}^r C_{r-1} P(0) + {}^{r-1} C_{r-1} P(1)$$

$$F^{r*}(1) = {}^{r-1} C_{r-1} P(0)$$

summing up left and right sides separately we find that the

$$\text{LHS} = F^{(r+1)*}(p^\alpha)$$

The RHS contains $\alpha + 1$ terms in which $P(0)$ occurs, α terms in which $P(1)$ occurs etc.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{RHS} = & \left[\sum_{k=0}^{\alpha} {}^{r+k-1} C_{r-1} \right] P(0) + \sum_{k=0}^{\alpha-1} {}^{r+k-1} C_{r-1} P(1) + \dots + \sum_{k=0}^1 {}^{r+k-1} C_{r-1} P(\alpha-1) \\ & + \sum_{k=0}^0 {}^{r+k-1} C_{r-1} P(\alpha) \end{aligned}$$

Applying proposition (4.2) to each of the Σ we get

$$\begin{aligned} \text{RHS} = & {}^{r+\alpha} C_r P(0) + {}^{r+\alpha-1} C_r P(1) + {}^{r+\alpha-2} C_r P(2) + \dots + {}^r C_r P(\alpha) \\ = & \sum_{k=0}^{\alpha} {}^{r+k} C_r P(\alpha-k) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{or } F^{(r+1)*}(p^\alpha) = \sum_{k=0}^{\alpha} {}^{r+k} C_r P(\alpha-k)$$

The proposition is true for $n = r+1$, as we have

$$F^{r*}(p^\alpha) = \sum_{k=0}^{\alpha} P(\alpha-k) = \sum_{k=0}^{\alpha} {}^k C_0 P(\alpha-k) = \sum_{k=0}^{\alpha} {}^{k+1-1} C_{1-1} P(\alpha-k)$$

The proposition is true for $n = 1$

Hence by induction the proposition is true for all n .

This completes the proof of theorem (4.1).

Following theorem shall be applied in the proof of theorem (4.3)

THEOREM (4.2)

$n-r$

$$\sum_{k=0}^n {}^n C_{r+k} {}^{r+k} C_r m^k = {}^n C_r (1+m)^{(n-r)}$$

PROOF:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{LHS} &= \sum_{k=0}^{n-r} {}^n C_{r+k} {}^{r+k} C_r m^k \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{n-r} \frac{(n!)}{\{(r+k)! \cdot (n-r-k)!\}} \cdot \frac{(r+k)!}{\{(k)! \cdot (r)!\}} \cdot m^k \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{n-r} \frac{(n!)}{\{(r)! \cdot (n-r)!\}} \cdot \frac{(n-r)!}{\{(k)! \cdot (n-r-k)!\}} \cdot m^k \\ &= {}^n C_r \sum_{k=0}^{n-r} {}^{n-r} C_k m^k \\ &= {}^n C_r (1+m)^{(n-r)} \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of theorem (4.2)

THEOREM(4.3):

$$F^{m*}(1\#n) = \sum_{r=0}^n {}^n C_r m^{n-r} F(1\#r)$$

Proof:

From theorem (2.4) (ref.[1] ne have

$$F^*(1\#n) = F(1\#(n+1)) = \sum_{r=0}^n {}^n C_r F(1\#r) = \sum_{r=0}^n {}^n C_r (1)^{n-r} F(1\#r)$$

hence the proposition is true for $m = 1$.

Let the proposition be true for $m = s$. Then we have

$$F^{s*}(1\#n) = \sum_{r=0}^n {}^n C_r s^{n-r} F(1\#r)$$

or

$$F^{s*}(1\#0) = \sum_{r=0}^0 {}^0 C_0 s^{0-r} F(1\#0)$$

$$F^{s*}(1\#1) = \sum_{r=0}^1 {}^1 C_1 s^{1-r} F(1\#1)$$

$$F^{s*}(1\#2) = \sum_{r=0}^2 {}^2 C_2 s^{2-r} F(1\#1)$$

$$F^{s*}(1\#3) = \sum_{r=0}^3 {}^3 C_1 s^{3-r} F(1\#3)$$

$$F^{s^*(1\#0)} = {}^0C_0 F(1\#0) \quad \text{----(0)}$$

$$F^{s^*(1\#1)} = {}^1C_0 s^1 F(1\#0) + {}^1C_1 s^0 F(1\#1) \quad \text{----(1)}$$

$$F^{s^*(1\#2)} = {}^2C_0 s^2 F(1\#0) + {}^2C_1 s^1 F(1\#1) + {}^2C_2 s^0 F(1\#2) \quad \text{----(2)}$$

⋮
⋮
⋮

$$F^{s^*(1\#r)} = {}^rC_0 s^r F(1\#0) + {}^rC_1 s^1 F(1\#1) + \dots + {}^rC_r s^0 F(1\#r) \quad \text{----(r)}$$

⋮
⋮
⋮

$$F^{s^*(1\#n)} = {}^nC_0 s^n F(1\#0) + {}^nC_1 s^{n-1} F(1\#1) + \dots + {}^nC_n s^0 F(1\#n) \quad \text{----(n)}$$

multiplying the r^{th} equation with nC_r and then summing up we get the RHS as

$$= [{}^nC_0 {}^0C_0 s^0 + {}^nC_1 {}^1C_0 s^1 + {}^nC_2 {}^2C_0 s^2 + \dots + {}^nC_k {}^kC_0 s^k + \dots + {}^nC_n {}^nC_0 s^n] F(1\#0)$$

$$[{}^nC_1 {}^1C_1 s^0 + {}^nC_2 {}^2C_1 s^1 + {}^nC_3 {}^3C_1 s^2 + \dots + {}^nC_k {}^kC_1 s^k + \dots + {}^nC_n {}^nC_1 s^n] F(1\#1)$$

⋮

$$[{}^nC_r {}^rC_r s^0 + {}^nC_{r+1} {}^{r+1}C_r s^1 + \dots + {}^nC_{r+k} {}^{r+k}C_r s^k + \dots + {}^nC_n {}^nC_r s^n] F(1\#r)$$

$$+ {}^nC_n {}^nC_n s^0] F(1\#n)$$

$$= \sum_{r=0}^n \left\{ \sum_{k=0}^{n-r} {}^nC_{r+k} {}^{r+k}C_r s^k \right\} F(1\#r)$$

$$= \sum_{r=0}^n {}^nC_r (1+s)^{n-r} F(1\#n) \quad , \text{ by theorem (4.2)}$$

$$\text{LHS} = \sum_{r=0}^n {}^nC_r F^{s^*(1\#r)}$$

Let $N = p_1 p_2 p_3 \dots p_n$. Then there are nC_r divisors of N containing exactly r primes. Then LHS = the sum of the s^{th} Smarandache star functions of all the divisors of N . $= F^{(s+1)^*(N)} = F^{(s+1)^*(1\#n)}$.

Hence we have

$$F^{(s+1)^*(1\#n)} = \sum_{r=0}^n {}^nC_r (1+s)^{n-r} F(1\#n)$$

$$F^{s*}(1\#0) = {}^0C_0 F(1\#0) \quad \text{----(0)}$$

$$F^{s*}(1\#1) = {}^1C_0 s^1 F(1\#0) + {}^1C_1 s^0 F(1\#1) \quad \text{----(1)}$$

$$F^{s*}(1\#2) = {}^2C_0 s^2 F(1\#0) + {}^2C_1 s^1 F(1\#1) + {}^2C_2 s^0 F(1\#2) \quad \text{----(2)}$$

$$\vdots$$

$$F^{s*}(1\#r) = {}^rC_0 s^r F(1\#0) + {}^rC_1 s^1 F(1\#1) + \dots + {}^rC_r s^0 F(1\#r) \quad \text{----(r)}$$

$$\vdots$$

$$F^{s*}(1\#n) = {}^nC_0 s^n F(1\#0) + {}^nC_1 s^{n-1} F(1\#1) + \dots + {}^nC_n s^0 F(1\#n) \quad \text{----(n)}$$

multiplying the r^{th} equation with nC_r and then summing up we get the RHS as

$$= [{}^nC_0 {}^0C_0 s^0 + {}^nC_1 {}^1C_0 s^1 + {}^nC_2 {}^2C_0 s^2 + \dots + {}^nC_k {}^kC_0 s^k + \dots + {}^nC_n {}^nC_0 s^n] F(1\#0)$$

$$[{}^nC_1 {}^1C_1 s^0 + {}^nC_2 {}^2C_1 s^1 + {}^nC_3 {}^3C_1 s^2 + \dots + {}^nC_k {}^kC_1 s^k + \dots + {}^nC_n {}^nC_1 s^n] F(1\#1)$$

$$\dots$$

$$[{}^nC_r {}^rC_r s^0 + {}^nC_{r+1} {}^{r+1}C_r s^1 + \dots + {}^nC_{r+k} {}^{r+k}C_r s^k + \dots + {}^nC_n {}^nC_r s^n] F(1\#r)$$

$$+ {}^nC_n {}^nC_n s^0] F(1\#n)$$

$$= \sum_{r=0}^n \left\{ \sum_{k=0}^{n-r} {}^nC_{r+k} {}^{r+k}C_r s^k \right\} F(1\#r)$$

$$= \sum_{r=0}^n {}^nC_r (1+s)^{n-r} F(1\#n) \quad , \text{ by theorem (4.2)}$$

$$\text{LHS} = \sum_{r=0}^n {}^nC_r F^{s*}(1\#r)$$

Let $N = p_1 p_2 p_3 \dots p_n$. Then there are nC_r divisors of N containing exactly r primes. Then LHS = the sum of the s^{th} Smarandache star functions of all the divisors of N . $= F^{(s+1)*}(N) = F^{(s+1)*}(1\#n)$.

Hence we have

$$F^{(s+1)*}(1\#n) = \sum_{r=0}^n {}^nC_r (1+s)^{n-r} F(1\#n)$$

which takes the same format

$$P(s) \Rightarrow P(s+1)$$

and it has been verified that the proposition is true for $m = 1$

hence by induction the proposition is true for all m .

$$F^{m*}(1\#n) = \sum_{r=0}^n {}^n C_r m^{n-r} F(1\#r)$$

This completes the proof of theorem (4.3)

NOTE:

From theorem (3.1) we have

$$F'(N@1\#n) = F'(Np_1p_2 \dots p_n) = \sum_{m=0}^n a_{(n,m)} F'^{m*}(N)$$

where

$$a_{(n,m)} = (1/m!) \sum_{k=1}^m (-1)^{m-k} {}^m C_k \cdot k^n$$

If $N = p_1p_2 \dots p_k$ Then we get

$$F(1\#(k+n)) = \sum_{m=0}^n [a_{(n,m)} \sum_{t=0}^k {}^k C_t m^{k-t} F(1\#t)] \quad \text{-----(4.4)}$$

The above result provides us with a formula to express B_n in terms of smaller Bell numbers. It is in a way generalisation of theorem (2.4) in Ref [5].

THEOREM(4.4):

$$F(\alpha, 1\#(n+1)) = \sum_{k=0}^{\alpha} \sum_{r=0}^n {}^n C_r F(k, 1\#r)$$

PROOF: LHS = $F(\alpha, 1\#(n+1)) = F'(p^\alpha p_1p_2p_3 \dots p_{n+1}) = F'^*(p^\alpha p_1p_2p_3 \dots p_n) + \sum F'(\text{all the divisors containing only } p^0) + \sum F'(\text{all the$

divisors containing only p^1) + $\sum F'$ (all the divisors containing only p^2) + . . . + $\sum F'$ (all the divisors containing only p^r) + . . . + $\sum F'$ (all the divisors containing only p^α)

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \sum_{r=0}^n {}^n C_r F(0, 1\#r) + \sum_{r=0}^n {}^n C_r F(1, 1\#r) + \sum_{r=0}^n {}^n C_r F(2, 1\#r) + \sum_{r=0}^n {}^n C_r F(3, 1\#r) \\
 &+ \dots + \sum_{r=0}^n {}^n C_r F(k, 1\#r) + \dots + \sum_{r=0}^n {}^n C_r F(\alpha, 1\#r) \\
 &= \sum_{k=0}^{\alpha} \sum_{r=0}^n {}^n C_r F(k, 1\#r)
 \end{aligned}$$

This is a reduction formula for $F(\alpha, 1\#(n+1))$

A Result of significance

From theorem (3.1) of Ref.: [2] , we have

$$F'(p^\alpha @ 1\#(n+1)) = F(\alpha, 1\#(n+1)) = \sum_{m=0}^n a_{(n+1,m)} F'^{m*}(N)$$

where

$$a_{(n+1,m)} = (1/m!) \sum_{k=1}^m (-1)^{m-k} \cdot {}^m C_k \cdot k^{n+1}$$

and

$$F'^{m*}(p^\alpha) = \sum_{k=0}^{\alpha} {}^{m+k-1} C_{m-1} P(\alpha-k)$$

This is the first result of some substance , giving a formula for evaluating the number of Smarandache Factor Partitions of numbers representable in a (one of the most simple) particular canonical form. The complexity is evident. The challenging task ahead for the readers is to derive similar expressions for other canonical forms.

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